

THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS IN THE SYSTEM OF ETHNOCULTURAL DETERMINANTS OF NEGATIVE SYMPTOMS OF PARANOID SCHIZOPHRENIA

¹Suleymanov S.R., ²Rogov A.V., ³Irmukhamedov T.B.

Annotation. *The article presents the results of a study of negative symptoms in patients with paranoid schizophrenia, taking into account the role of environmentally unfavorable factors in the system of ethnocultural communications, a comparative assessment of the psychometric study of negative symptoms in patients with paranoid schizophrenia. The data on the allocation of the dimensions of negative symptoms and a differentiated assessment of their role for the social functioning of patients with schizophrenia in the conditions of unfavorable environmental factors of the Aral Sea region are presented.*

Keywords: *paranoid schizophrenia, ethnocultural psychiatry, negative symptoms, Aral Sea region.*

The problem of diagnostic assessment of mental disorders, which is crucial for the prognosis of the disease, the choice of therapy and rehabilitation measures, remains one of the most relevant in modern psychiatry and is due, as numerous studies show, not so much to differences in the interpretation of psychopathological conditions and the content of terms, during the widespread unification and use of the international classification of diseases, this is not so relevant, and in a certain heterogeneity of the leading syndrome complexes that clinicians face in the field. The development of the concept of the biopsychosocial model of the disease contributed to a new understanding of the therapeutic and preventive process. Full functional and social recovery of the patient can be achieved with a comprehensive understanding of the totality of the individual's disorders and the development of appropriate medical rehabilitation effects, and not only by relieving painful symptoms. (Hritinin D. F., 2015). One of the least studied aspects of this problem is the role of ethnocultural factors in the prevalence, formation, clinic and course of paranoid schizophrenia. The essence and understanding of schizophrenia cannot be achieved without taking into account the ethnic traditional way of life of the studied patient population, ethnogenesis and peculiarities of adaptation to environmental conditions (V.Ya. Semke). Insufficient attention to the role of such important ethnocultural factors often leads to gross diagnostic errors, incorrect therapeutic tactics and incorrect planning of preventive measures (O.A. Gilburd). J. Leff expressed the opinion that the process of cultural integration determines the clinical pathomorphosis of schizophrenia. This is manifested by a gradual increase in the representation of ideational symptoms, the emergence of new delusional plots related to cultural innovations. Of course, ethnocultural factors are important patterns in the specific pathomorphosis tracks of the endogenous process. Scientific research in this field shows that a comprehensive study of ethnic and socio-cultural factors of mental health, psychiatric care and prevention can be the key to understanding the fundamental foundations of the formation of psychopathology, since long-term exposure to natural factors specific to each ethnic group determines the ecobiological and socio-cultural features of syndrome formation in various ethnic groups.

The concept of negative and positive symptoms has changed repeatedly throughout the twentieth century. Moreover, for quite a long time, negative symptoms were interpreted extremely narrowly as symptoms of a defect or dementia, recognizing them as irreversible. To verify

deficiency disorders, use the chronodynamic criterion, which implies the persistence of symptoms during the period of remission of schizophrenia. At the same time, according to S.N. According to Mosolova, the criteria for the persistence and irreversibility of deficiency disorders, as well as the specificity of initial conditions, are not generally accepted today and deficiency symptoms should be understood as relatively persistent specific disorders that persist throughout the disease from premorbid to remission and demonstrate resistance to therapy. At the same time, negative symptoms are one of the most studied problems in schizophrenia, however, with seemingly comprehensive study, there remain literally huge, unexplored "white spots" about which there are controversial battles among scientists. The negative portrait of a patient with paranoid schizophrenia is presented in the form of a heterogeneous palette with many initial determinants that determine the final profile of deficiency symptoms. And if a huge number of studies have been devoted to the influence of biological, constitutional and social factors on the manifestations of deficiency symptoms, then ethnocultural factors have remained in the shadows until recently. Small, timid studies of this issue show great promise in a comprehensive study of the heterogeneity of negative symptoms.

The purpose of the study to identify the features of the deficit symptoms of paranoid schizophrenia, taking into account ethnocultural and environmentally unfavorable factors.

Materials and methods of research

72 patients were examined with a verified diagnosis in accordance with ICD-10 paranoid schizophrenia (F-20.xx), with an average disease duration of 12 ± 3.2 years. The presented sample of patients was characterized by: the average age was 45.22 ± 11.39 years ($p < 0.05$), the minimum age was 23 years, the maximum was 49 years.

The respondents made up two comparable groups according to biological and social factors, 37 respondents were groups of patients with paranoid schizophrenia from the Aral Sea regions (gP) and 35 patients with paranoid schizophrenia from the city of Tashkent (gT).

In order to avoid unreliable and contradictory data related to the peculiarity of various psychometric scales and their insufficient validity and adaptation, the assessment of negative symptoms in the studied respondents was carried out using the classic PANSS test- The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (Stanley Kay, Lewis Opler, and Abraham Fiszbein).

The PANSS clinical rating scale is designed for the quantitative and structural assessment of positive and negative psychopathological syndromes in accordance with the concept of T. Crowe (1980) and Nancy Andreasen (1982). The scale consists of 33 items (symptoms) assessed based on a formal semi-structured or fully structured clinical interview and other sources of information. The severity of the symptom is assessed according to a 7-point system. For each symptom and gradations of its severity, a thorough operational definition and precise instructions for its detection are given. Since PANSS primarily serves to accurately assess the positive and negative characteristics of the schizophrenic spectrum, which are postulated by T. Crowe (1980) and N. Andreasen, S. Olsen (1982), seven symptoms are grouped into a scale of positive syndromes that assess signs that are excessive to the "normal" mental status, the other seven symptoms make up the scale of negative syndromes evaluating signs that are insufficient for a "normal" mental status. The composite index (the difference between the sum of the scores of positive and negative symptoms) determines the degree of predominance of one syndrome over another. The scale allows for a standardized assessment of various vectors of psychopathological symptoms of schizophrenia, to determine the clinical profile of the patient and to trace the

dynamics of the condition during therapy. The scale allows you to quantify the severity of negative symptoms on a Scale of negative symptoms.

Results. The dimensional characteristics of patients with paranoid schizophrenia, using the PANSS psychometric scale, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of deficiency symptoms in patients with paranoid schizophrenia of both groups at the time of examination

The PANSS indicator Negative symptoms	$\mu \pm \sigma$, the predominance of the average cv*	
	rII n=37	rT n=35
H1 "Dumb affect"	3,26±0,74	4,85±0,92
H2 Emotional care	3,11±0,70	4,55±0,95
H3 The poverty of emotional connections	3,23±0,73	5,10±1,19
H4 Passive/apathetic social withdrawal into oneself	3,00±0,82	4,78±0,92
H5 Violation of abstract thinking	2,53±0,80	3,98±1,49
H6 Lack of spontaneity and free flow of conversation	1,19±0,58	2,42±1,05
H7 Stereotypical (rigid) thinking	1,02±0,13	1,08±0,28
Severity of negative symptoms ΣN	17,33±2,17	26,77±4,60

It follows from the data in the table that the psychometric indicators of deficiency symptoms in patients with paranoid schizophrenia in both groups significantly differ. The results of the analysis of the cluster "negative symptoms" showed that in patients of the group of patients from the Aral Sea region, such indicators as "dull affect", "emotional care" and "poverty of emotional connections" were significantly expressed and for 53.6%, 39.3% and 44%, respectively, they were 5.4 and 6 points, which is high on the scale PANSS. The severity of "passive-apathetic withdrawal into oneself" in patients of the main group was expressed in points with a high coefficient of 5 and was relevant for 54.8% of the subjects of this group, while in the group of patients from Tashkent, 59.6% of respondents had this indicator equal to 2. Violations of "abstract thinking" in the control group for 77.1% of patients it was significantly higher than in the GP. The other indicators were not significantly different. It should be emphasized that it is the indicators H1, H2, H3, H4 that characterize the social adaptation of patients and reflect the social intelligence of patients, which is an integral part of cognitive functioning. The assessment of the overall severity of negative symptoms deserves close attention. For patients of the main group, it is 26.48±4.41 points, while in the control group this indicator is at the level of 17.33 ± 2.17 points. Clinical analysis of deficiency symptoms revealed symptoms such as: emotional detachment is manifested by a lack of interest in life phenomena, participation in them and a sense of emotional involvement in them. The severity is assessed based on information received from medical staff and relatives, as well as on the results of monitoring the patient's behavior during the conversation. Passive-apathetic social isolation is manifested by a decrease in interest and initiative in social relations due to passivity, apathy, loss of energy and volitional impulses, which leads to a decrease in sociability and neglect of daily activities. Violations of abstract thinking are defined by a disorder of abstract-symbolic thinking, manifested in difficulty in classifying and generalizing, as well as in the inability to get away from specific or egocentric ways of solving problems.

The parameters that determine social functioning and quality of life are currently considered as the most universal indicators of an individual's well-being, negative symptoms are crucial in the re-socialization of patients with paranoid schizophrenia. In the study of adaptation mechanisms during remission in patients with schizophrenia, E.D. Krasik and G.V. Logvinovich

(1991) described the levels of clinical and social adaptation: integrative, destructive, extroverted and introverted.

The group of patients with an integrative type of adaptation is 39% of patients from the gT group. This group consisted of patients with a relatively predominance of positive symptoms and had a moderate level of social adaptation and more loyal compliance.

The group of patients with a destructive type of adaptation is 43% of patients in the gP group. Characteristic of this group of patients was a high degree of severity of negative disorders, the presence of residual psychoproductive symptoms, frequent exacerbations of the disease with the formation of low-quality remissions, without criticism of the psychosis suffered, and a low level of social functioning.

Conclusions. Thus, the data presented show that in the case of a dimensional analysis of psychometric indicators, patients with different ethnocultural characteristics significantly differ from each other. The integrative type of adaptation prevailed in the group of patients from the city of Tashkent, the destructive type of adaptation was more typical for the group of patients from the Aral Sea region.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Rogov A. et al. Recreational use of psychoactive substances in the manifest period of paranoid schizophrenia in adolescents //Science and innovation. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. D2. – С. 70-75.
2. Rogov A. V. et al. Some determinants of disturbances of social functioning in patients with paranoid schizophrenia with related viral hepatitis //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 5. – С. 425-433.
3. Rogov A. V. et al. Some determinants of disturbances of social functioning in patients with paranoid schizophrenia with related viral hepatitis //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 5. – С. 425-433.
4. Rogov A. V. Choice strategy disorders in patients with paranoid schizophrenia with concomitant viral hepatitis.
5. Rogov A. V. Clinical features of cerebral vascular reactivity with negative symptoms in patients with paranoid schizophrenia //Science and Innovation. 2024. Т. 3. –№. 4. – С. 86-93.
6. Rogov A. V., Abdullayeva V. K. Determinant of social functioning in patients with paranoid schizophrenia with concomitant viral hepatitis //Materials of International Scientific-Practical Conference. – 2022. – С. 73.
7. Vladimirovich R. A., Aleksandrovna M. A. UDC: 616.895. 87 Violations of the planning strategy in patients with paranoid schizophrenia with related viral hepatitis //ВВК. – 2020. – Т. 57. – С. 112.
8. Ирмухамедов Т. Б., Абдуллаева В. К. клинико-динамические особенности пациентов параноидной шизофренией с сопутствующими церебрально-гемодинамическими нарушениями //Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности. – 2020. – С. 174-181.
9. Ирмухамедов Т. Б., Абдуллаева В. К., Рогов А. В. Динамические аспекты когнитивных нарушений у детей с расстройствами аутистического спектра //Актуальные вопросы психиатрии и наркологии в современных условиях. – 2023. – С. 78-81.
10. Ирмухамедов Т. Б., Абдуллаева В. К., Рогов А. В. Клинический портрет когнитивных нарушений у детей с расстройствами аутистического спектра //Ошибки и заблуждения в психиатрии. – 2023. – С. 58-60.

11. Рогов А. В. Индивидуально типологические предикторы когнитивных нарушений в манифестный период параноидной шизофрении. – 2022.
12. Рогов А. В., Абдуллаева В. К. Особенности проблемно-решающего поведения у больных параноидной шизофренией с сопутствующими вирусными гепатитами //Новый день в медицине. – 2019. – №. 2. – С. 47-49.
13. Рогов А. В., Абдуллаева В. К. Особенности социальной адаптации и качества жизни больных параноидной шизофренией, сочетанной с хроническими вирусными гепатитами //Актуальные проблемы психиатрии и наркологии в современных условиях. – 2020. – С. 119-120.
14. Рогов А. В., Абдуллаева В. К. Характеристики стратегии выбора у больных параноидной шизофренией с сопутствующими вирусными гепатитами //Актуальные вопросы фундаментальной и клинической медицины. – 2020. – С. 419-422.
15. Рогов А. Особенности социальной ангедонии в структуре дефицитарных расстройств больных параноидной шизофренией //Биопсихосоциальная психиатрия: новые подходы и перспективы развития. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 39-40.
16. Рогов А. Структура аффективных расстройств у больных параноидной шизофренией, ассоциированной со стрессом //Биопсихосоциальная психиатрия: новые подходы и перспективы развития. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 41-42.